

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Norqulova Jasmina Sherzod qizi

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH. BEST PRACTICES FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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